

METHODS OF ORGANIZING TRAINING IN VOLLEYBALL PLAYERS

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Annotation

The article discusses issues related to the methodology of training young volleyball players in modern conditions. The author focuses on the versatile physical and technical training of children based on mastering the elements of volleyball and other sports

Key words

athletes, training, upbringing, volleyball, preliminary training, physical qualities of a child

Volleyball as a sports game appeared at the end of the 19th century. Its creator is physical education teacher William Morgan from the USA. He wanted the game to not require complicated equipment, to have simple rules, to be accessible to people of any age, and proposed the rules of a new game developed by him. At the beginning of the 20th century, volleyball became famous in many countries of Central and South America, in Canada. In 1913, volleyball was included in the program of the Spartakiads of South and North America, and on the eve of the First World War it appeared in Europe. In the early 50s, volleyball was introduced in Russia, but the game received the greatest ground for its development after the Great October Socialist Revolution. Volleyball is played on a 9x18 m playground.

The entire site is divided into two equal halves by a middle line, above which the grid rises. The height of the net depends on the age and gender of the players. Volleyball occupies a worthy place in the system of physical education. The advantage of volleyball lies in the comparative simplicity of the equipment of the places for the game and the rules of its conduct with great entertainment. The abundance of various tactical combinations, the emotionality of the struggle, collectivism, that's what attracts millions of people of different ages and professions in volleyball. Volleyball is a very effective means of promoting health and physical development. With proper organization of classes, volleyball helps to strengthen the musculoskeletal system and improve all body functions.

The intensity of a sports match, the desire to overcome difficulties in the struggle for victory contributes to the development of such valuable qualities as

courage, perseverance, determination, dedication, initiative, discipline. The need for concerted efforts to achieve a common goal during the game teaches the player to collective actions, the desire for mutual assistance, fosters a sense of friendship and camaraderie. Technical training of volleyball players, especially young ones, at the stages of initial training, is very necessary for the purpose of high-quality preparation and successful performances at local competitions, and begins at school age, where the foundation of physical and especially technical training is laid. The main emphasis in the training of young volleyball players should be placed on the development of physical, functional and technical qualities necessary for volleyball players to train high-class athletes. Tasks: To determine the level of technical preparedness of young volleyball players. training volleyball training ball 1 Organization of the training process of young volleyball players

In order to create a volleyball section and attract as many people as possible to classes at school with younger boys, it is advisable to hold some events in the team. You can start by showing a movie about volleyball competitions, such as the World Cup, at an evening or after a general meeting. Then a meeting is held with famous volleyball players of the country, the city, the best coaches who talk about volleyball, about interesting episodes from their sports practice, about what volleyball classes give. At the end of the evening, it is good to hold an exhibition game of the best teams of the district or youth sports school. All this causes great interest in volleyball among those present, which is very important then to strengthen and deepen through the skillful conduct of practical exercises.

Training sessions in the section are conducted in the form of lessons according to a generally accepted scheme according to a schedule drawn up taking into account the employment of those engaged in industrial and educational activities, and the available material base. In addition, it is advisable for students to give tasks for independent, more detailed improvement of individual techniques of the game technique, increasing physical fitness, strengthening health and hardening the body, Throughout the year in the process of training sessions, preparations are being made for passing the presidential standards. For beginners and athletes of youth categories, the norms are fulfilled in training sessions (according to the section of physical training). And for athletes of the 2nd and 3rd youth categories, control standards for general and special physical training are accepted [1].

The main tasks facing the training groups of beginners (the first year of classes): instilling interest in volleyball and fostering sports diligence; strengthening health, comprehensive physical and psychological training based on mastering and passing presidential tests. the development of the qualities necessary for a volleyball player - speed, strength, endurance, dexterity; the study of basic techniques of the game and the simplest tactical actions in attack and defense; the acquisition of experience in competitions (participation in competitions of the physical education team). The main tasks facing the study groups of youth categories (the next year of classes): further improvement of the level of comprehensive physical fitness, development of the qualities necessary for a volleyball player - strength, speed, endurance, dexterity, speed and jumping endurance; passing the standards of presidential tests; compliance with standards for general and special physical training; assimilation of basic theoretical information in accordance with the requirements of the program; further study and improvement of techniques and tactics of the game; compliance with the norms youth sports categories; acquisition of experience in participating in regional competitions and improvement of tactical skills; acquisition of knowledge and skills of practical judging of competitions. further improvement of technical techniques and tactical actions in attack and defense in a game environment;

fulfillment of special requirements for technical training; accumulation of experience in participating in competitions; acquisition of experience in independently conducting training, drawing up individual training plans; acquisition of instructional skills in organizing and conducting training sessions, obtaining the title of a public volleyball coach; - acquisition of knowledge and skills of practical refereeing competitions, obtaining the title of a sports judge. For students of all groups, it is mandatory to take tests on theoretical training [2].

When developing annual plans for training sessions of sections, due attention should be paid to the following basic provisions: continuity and year-round organization of the training process; a clear definition of the tasks and content of training sessions for individual periods and stages of the training year; definition for each group of means and methods of physical, technical, tactical and theoretical training in accordance with sports the qualification of those involved and the task of further growth of their sports skills; to determine the content and means of moral, volitional and psychological training of students; to organize educational work; to organize medical and pedagogical control; to

determine for each group a plan for participation in calendar competitions of the year, the formation and training of teams; to determine the level of training and competitive loads for individual groups of students, depending on their sports qualifications.

In the content of volitional and psychological training, the main attention is paid to increasing the tolerance of training loads, individual training tools and the adaptation of teams to upcoming competitions. Theoretical training provides for the study of materials, the general basics of training, the analysis of diary entries, the performance of individual tasks, speaking at theoretical classes with messages on various topics of technical and tactical training. At the end of this stage, control tests on physical and technical training, control and friendly meetings are held, in which the technical and tactical skills of the team and individual players are checked.

The dynamics of the load is characterized by a decrease in the total volume and a further increase in its intensity to the competitive level and above [3]. Physical training is aimed at achieving high fitness, maintaining it at this level, as well as maintaining the achieved overall fitness. Technical training should ensure further improvement of the accuracy, speed and stability of the application of techniques in difficult conditions. Tactical training clarifies the forms of playing the game and the actions of individual players, taking into account the game of a particular opponent, and eliminates the shortcomings identified in previous meetings. The overall proportion of physical, technical and tactical training remains at the level of the pre-competition stage. Psychological training should ensure maximum mobilization and readiness of the volleyball player for each calendar game and competitions in general. In moral and volitional training, attention is focused on the development of volitional qualities associated with the player's direct participation in competitions: the will to win, endurance, courage and determination in game actions, the will to overcome negative emotions during competitions (self-doubt, fear of acting decisively and actively in the most crucial moments of the game, depression, related to individual failures).

Theoretical training is aimed at studying the features of training in the competitive period, as well as at expanding knowledge that contributes to the successful growth of sports skills and performance in competitions. The means used in the competitive period are mainly special game exercises; two-sided games; exercises of special physical training; improvements in the technique of game techniques; group and team tactical actions. The number of classes for 1-2

calendar games per week is no more than three. The total volume of loads decreases slightly and then stabilizes, and their intensity increases to a maximum and stabilizes at this level [4]. Organizational and methodological guidelines The entire process of educational and training work should ensure a high level of mastery of the technique of playing volleyball, the development of physical qualities (strength, speed, endurance, dexterity), the education of strong-willed character traits, strengthening the health of those involved and on this basis achieving high sports skills. All these points should be taken into account in the education and training of volleyball players in various training groups. Educational work is carried out according to the action plans of the physical culture team, the sports club, but mainly it is carried out directly in the course of classes of the section and participation in competitions. Any activity of the sports section, every competition should solve educational tasks.

The main form of conducting training sessions is training. Clear organization and use of the group form of classes, observance of order when performing exercises contribute to improving the organization and discipline of students. As a rule, general and special physical training tools and exercises should be widely used in all training sessions [5]. To achieve technical mastery, it is necessary to regularly combine training sessions with the ball with other sports: athletics, swimming, gymnastics and especially acrobatics. Acrobatics classes will allow you to quickly master the techniques of the game and further improve it. Game techniques should be learned in combination with various complex acrobatic exercises that require players to have well-developed coordination of movements, dexterity, flexibility and other qualities. Mastering game techniques in more complex combinations than those found in the game creates confidence in the students that in a less difficult environment they will be able to successfully apply these techniques. Acrobatic training should be considered as one of the main means of individual physical improvement and improving the athletic skills of volleyball players. Classes should be organized in such a way that volleyball players learn something new at each of them.

This also applies to the improvement of tactical combinations and tactics of individual techniques (for example, the tactics of submission or offensive strike). In the process of training sessions with volleyball players, it is necessary to pay great attention to acrobatic exercises, combining them with exercises in throwing for accuracy and range, as well as with ball transfers in various directions. To improve the strength and speed of the offensive strike, you need to select special exercises such as throwing objects of various weights. The main

thing is that training sessions are systematically conducted in sports sections, and sports competitions and friendly meetings are held according to a certain plan. Only under these conditions can qualified athletes be trained. Special endurance combines speed, jumping and gaming endurance. It depends on the level of development of general endurance, the fitness of the musculoskeletal system, the strength of mental processes (for example, the ability to endure), and the economy of sports equipment. Speed endurance is the ability of a volleyball player to perform techniques and move at high speed throughout the game.

In addition, the accuracy of the movements performed must be maximum, otherwise technical errors are inevitable. A number of techniques are performed in an unsupported position, which places high demands on the activity of the vestibular apparatus. This requires high development of special dexterity and precision of movements in space. The agility of a volleyball player has two varieties: acrobatic agility, which manifests itself in falls, rolls during the game in defense; jumping dexterity is the ability to control your body in a secure position when performing attacking strikes, blocking and second passes in a jump [8]. 1.2 Means used in the development of physical qualities Physical qualities are understood as socially conditioned sets of biological and mental properties of a person, expressing his physical readiness to carry out active motor activity. The main physical qualities include strength, endurance, agility, flexibility, etc. Physical qualities differ from other personality traits in that they can only manifest themselves when solving motor tasks through motor actions.

Physical abilities are understood as relatively stable, innate and acquired functional capabilities of organs and structures of the body, the interaction of which determines the effectiveness of performing motor actions. Innate capabilities are determined by the corresponding inclinations, acquired by the socio-ecological environment of human life. At the same time, one physical ability can develop on the basis of different inclinations and, conversely, on the basis of the same inclinations, different abilities can arise. The realization of physical abilities in motor actions expresses the nature and level of development of the functional capabilities of individual organs and structures of the body. Therefore, a single physical ability cannot fully express the corresponding physical quality. The stated ideas about the essence of physical qualities and physical abilities allow us to conclude: a) the basis of the education of physical qualities is the development of physical abilities. The more developed the abilities expressing this physical quality, the more stable it is in solving motor

tasks; b), the development of physical abilities is conditioned by innate inclinations that determine the individual capabilities of the functional development of individual organs and structures of the body.

The more reliable the functional interaction of organs and structures of the body, the more stable the expression of the corresponding physical abilities in motor actions; c) the education of physical qualities is achieved through solving a variety of motor tasks, and the development of physical abilities - through the performance of motor tasks. The possibility of solving diverse motor tasks characterizes the comprehensive education of physical qualities, and the possibility of performing diverse motor actions with the necessary functional activity of organs and structures of the body speaks about the harmonious education of physical qualities[9]. As a physical quality, strength is expressed through a set of power abilities that provide a measure of a person's physical impact on external objects.

Exercises with maximum effort involve performing motor actions with marginal or near-marginal (90-95% of the maximum value) weights. This ensures maximum mobilization of the neuromuscular apparatus and the greatest increase in strength abilities. Extreme muscle tension requires the manifestation of great mental stress, leads to overexcitation of the nerve centers, as a result of which "extra" muscle groups are additionally included in the work to perform this exercise, making it difficult to improve the technique of movements. To develop speed and strength abilities, exercises are used to overcome the weight of one's own body (for example, jumping) and with external weights (for example, throwing stuffed balls). The most common methods of developing speed and strength abilities are the methods of repeated exercise and circular training. The method of repeating the exercise allows you to selectively develop certain groups. The circular training method provides a comprehensive effect on various muscle groups.

Exercises are selected in such a way that each subsequent series includes a new muscle group in the work, allows you to significantly increase the amount of load with strict alternation of work and rest [10] Endurance is expressed through a combination of physical abilities, maintaining the duration of work in various power zones: maximum, submaximal (near-limit), large and moderate loads. Each load zone has its own peculiar complex of reactions of organs and structures of the body.

The duration of mechanical work until complete fatigue can be divided into three phases: initial fatigue, compensated and decompensated fatigue. The first

phase is characterized by the appearance of initial signs of fatigue, the second - progressively deepening fatigue, maintaining a given intensity of work due to additional volitional efforts and a partial change in the structure of motor action (for example, a decrease in length and an increase in the pace of steps when running). The third phase is characterized by a high degree of fatigue, leading to a decrease in the intensity of work until it stops. In the theory and practice of physical education, general and special endurance are distinguished. General endurance is understood as long-term performance of work with optimal functional activity of the main life-supporting organs and structures of the body. This mode of operation is mainly provided by the ability to perform motor actions in a zone of moderate loads. The leading physical abilities expressing the quality of endurance include endurance to loads in the maximum, submaximal, large and moderate load zones. All these abilities have a single meter - the maximum operating time before the start of a decrease in its power [11].

Dexterity is expressed through a combination of coordination abilities, as well as the ability to perform motor actions with the necessary range of motion (mobility in the joints). Dexterity is brought up through training in motor actions and solving motor tasks that require constant changes in the structure of actions. When learning, a mandatory requirement is the novelty of the exercise being learned and the conditions of its application. The novelty element is supported by the coordination difficulty of the action and the creation of external conditions that make it difficult to perform the exercise. Solving motor tasks involves performing mastered motor actions in unfamiliar situations. Coordination abilities are associated with the ability to control movements in space and time and include: spatial orientation; accuracy of motion reproduction in terms of spatial, force and time parameters; static and dynamic equilibrium.

Spatial orientation implies: the preservation of ideas about the parameters of changes in external conditions (situations); the ability to rebuild motor action in accordance with these changes. A person does not just react to an external situation. He must take into account the possible dynamics of its change, predict upcoming events and, in this regard, build an appropriate action program aimed at achieving a positive result. The reproduction of spatial, power and temporal parameters of movements is manifested in the accuracy of performing motor actions. Their development is determined by the improvement of sensory (sensitive) mechanisms of movement regulation. The accuracy of spatial movements in various joints (simple coordination) progressively increases

when using exercises to reproduce poses, the parameters of which are set in advance.

The accuracy of reproducing the power and time parameters of a motor action is characterized by the ability to differentiate muscle efforts according to the task or necessity associated with the conditions of performing this exercise. The development of the accuracy of the time parameters of movements is aimed at improving the so-called sense of time, i.e. the ability to differentiate the time characteristics of motor action. Its development is provided by exercises that allow you to change the amplitude of movements in a large range, as well as cyclic exercises performed at different speeds of movement using technical means (for example, electrolyzers, metronomes, etc.). Exercises that allow you to change the duration of movements in a large range contribute to the development of this quality [11]. Speed is manifested through a set of high-speed abilities, including: a) the speed of motor reactions; b) the speed of a single movement, not burdened by external resistance; c) the frequency (tempo) of movements. Many physical abilities that characterize speed are part of other physical qualities, especially the quality of dexterity. Speed is brought up by solving a variety of motor tasks, the success of which is determined by the minimum time for performing a motor action.

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